

Capacity Gaps and Training Needs in Performance Evaluation: A Case of the Zanzibar M&E Workforce

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ABSTRACT: This study examines capacity gaps and training needs in performance evaluation within Zanzibar's Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workforce. Specifically, it investigates how capacity dimensions' skills, knowledge, resources, institutional support and training program attributes frequency, coverage, and relevance influence the quality of performance evaluation in public institutions. The study adopted a mixed methods research design, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to 150 M&E officers drawn from various ministries, departments, and agencies under the Zanzibar Development Plan (ZADEP). Qualitative data were obtained through key informant interviews, which provided in-depth insights to complement the quantitative findings. Descriptive statistics summarized respondents' perceptions, and multiple linear regression analysis tested the influence of the seven predictor variables on the quality of performance evaluation.

The findings revealed that the seven predictors jointly were explained by 53.8% of the variance in evaluation quality ($R^2 = 0.538$, $p < 0.001$). At the variable level, skills ($\beta = 0.178$, $p = 0.013$), knowledge ($\beta = 0.161$, $p = 0.020$), institutional support ($\beta = 0.147$, $p = 0.025$), training frequency ($\beta = 0.112$, $p =$

0.043) and training relevance ($\beta = 0.134$, $p = 0.028$) emerged as statically significant predictors of evaluation quality. In contrast resources ($p = 0.112$) and training coverage ($p = 0.089$) did not show statistically significant effects. These results indicate that continuous professional development, supported by strong institutional frameworks and relevant training, is essential for improving the accuracy, timeliness, and utilization of performance evaluations in Zanzibar's public sector.

The study concluded that strengthening technical competencies, enhancing institutional support, and providing regular and relevant training are critical for improving the quality of performance evaluation in Zanzibar's public sector. The findings underscore the importance of institutionalized M&E capacity development initiatives, stronger collaboration between government institutions, ZAMEA, and academic bodies, as well as the introduction of professional certification mechanisms to enhance evaluation practice and promote evidence-based decision-making in Zanzibar.

Keywords: *Capacity Building, Monitoring and Evaluation, Performance Evaluation, Training Programs, Institutional Support, Public Sector.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) has become an essential pillar of evidence based decision making and accountability within public and private sector organizations worldwide. Governments, international development agencies, and non-governmental organizations increasingly rely on robust performance evaluation systems to measure the effectiveness of policies, programs and projects.

Despite global recognition of its importance, capacity gaps continue to constrain the quality of performance evaluations. Many institutions lack adequately trained M&E professionals with the necessary technical, analytical and reporting skills. Studies conducted by the World Bank (2020) and OECD-DAC (2019) indicate that limited technical expertise, insufficient resources and weak institutional support remain among the most common barriers to effective M&E implementation globally. To address these challenges, countries have invested in continuous capacity development through training programs, knowledge sharing platforms and

certification initiatives such as the CLEAR initiative (Centers for Learning on Evaluation and Results) which aimed at strengthen the global M&E workforce.

Across Africa, M&E systems are increasingly being integrated into national development planning frameworks, such as Kenya's Vision 2030, Uganda's National Development Plan and South Africa's Government Wide Monitoring and Evaluation System (GWMES).

Nevertheless, a significant capacity gap persists in the continent's M&E sector. The African Evaluation Association (AfrEA) reports that many M&E practitioners face challenges related to inadequate training in data analysis, use of digital tools and evidence-based reporting.

Additionally, limited institutional support and inconsistent training opportunities have weakened the overall performance evaluation quality in government and NGO programs (AfrEA, 2022).

In Tanzania, the demand for reliable performance evaluation systems has grown following the government's adoption of Results-Based Management (RBM) and the establishment of the National Framework for Monitoring and Evaluation (2015). Although these efforts have strengthened the national evaluation architecture, studies such as URT (2020) and REPOA (2021) reveal that Tanzania continues to face challenges related to human resource capacity, financial allocation, and training coverage. Many M&E officers at regional and district levels lack sufficient training in modern evaluation tools, data quality assurance, and statistical analysis. Consequently, this affects the timeliness, utilization and accuracy of performance reports across various sectors.

In Zanzibar, Monitoring and Evaluation has become increasingly important in tracking the implementation of the Zanzibar Development Vision 2050 and Zanzibar Strategy for Growth and Reduction of Poverty (ZSGRP III – MKUZA III) for the previous years. However, just like the mainland, the Zanzibar M&E system faces critical capacity gaps particularly in technical skills, data management and institutional coordination. Limited training opportunities, inadequate resource allocation and insufficient institutional support mechanisms have hindered the effectiveness of performance evaluation practices.

These challenges underscore the need for a systematic assessment of capacity gaps and training needs among M&E personnel in Zanzibar. The problem that this study addresses is the lack of empirical evidence on how capacity dimensions specifically skills, knowledge, resources, and institutional support along with training attributes such as frequency, coverage and relevance, affect the quality of performance evaluation within Zanzibar's public sector institutions. Without this understanding, efforts to strengthen the M&E workforce remain fragmented and unsustainable.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to examine the influence of capacity dimensions and training programs on the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce. Specifically, the study seeks to determine (i) the extent to which skills, knowledge, resources, and institutional support influence performance evaluation quality; (ii) whether training programs mediate the relationship between capacity dimensions and performance evaluation quality; and (iii) the overall effect of training programs on evaluation outcomes in Zanzibar's public institutions.

So, this study seeks to examine the relationship between capacity dimensions, training programs and the quality of performance evaluation within the Zanzibar M&E workforce.

H₀₁: Capacity dimensions (skills, knowledge, resources and institutional support) do not significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce. H₀₂: Training programs (frequency, coverage and relevance) do not mediate the relationship between capacity dimensions and the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce. H₀₃: Training programs do not significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Background of the Study Area

This study was conducted in Zanzibar, a semi-autonomous region of the United Republic of Tanzania located in the western Indian Ocean, approximately 35 kilometers off the mainland coast (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The region

comprises two main islands Unguja and Pemba along with several smaller islets. Zanzibar covers a total land area of about 2,654 square kilometers and has an estimated population of 1.9 million people (OCGS, 2023). Administratively, the islands are divided into five regions and eleven districts, each with distinct governance and development planning structures (Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar, 2022).

The economy of Zanzibar is primarily driven by tourism, clove production, fishing and small scale trade (World Bank, 2020). In recent years, the Government of Zanzibar has emphasized principles of good governance, transparency and results based management as part of its broader development agenda (RGoZ, 2021). Within this context, Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) has been integrated into public programs and projects through the **Zanzibar Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning Framework (Z-MELF)**, coordinated by the President's Office State House and President's Office Finance and Planning (RGoZ, 2022).

This institutional setup makes Zanzibar a relevant setting for examining issues of capacity, training and performance evaluation within the public sector. The region's ongoing commitment to results based management and evidence informed decision making provides a practical environment for assessing how human capacity and institutional support influence the quality of M&E practices across government Ministries and departments.

3.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of this study is grounded in two major theories; The Human Capital Theory and the Capacity Development Framework. The Human Capital Theory, developed by Becker (1993), postulates that individuals and organizations can enhance productivity and performance through investments in education, skills, and training. According to this theory, training and capacity building are not costs but strategic investments that yield long term benefits in the form of improved efficiency, innovation, and output quality. In the context of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E), this theory suggests that well trained personnel

are more capable of designing, implementing and assessing programs effectively which leads to higher-quality performance evaluations. Empirical evidence supports this view, indicating that continuous professional training contributes to improved data management, analytical ability, and decision-making within public sector organizations (Schultz, 2018; Mtega & Malekani, 2021).

The Capacity Development Framework by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2009) emphasizes that capacity exists at three interrelated levels; individual, institutional and systemic. The individual level involves developing technical skills, knowledge and competencies. The institutional level relates to improving organizational structures, tools, and processes that support performance and the systemic level focuses on enabling environments such as policies, governance structures and coordination mechanisms. This framework highlights that sustainable performance improvement requires addressing capacity gaps across all three levels simultaneously. For M&E systems in Zanzibar, this means not only training staff but also ensuring that institutions have the policies, resources and coordination necessary for effective performance evaluation (UNDP, 2020; RGoZ, 2021).

Together, these theories provide a comprehensive lens for this study. The Human Capital Theory explains how investments in people through relevant and frequent training can improve performance evaluation quality, while the Capacity Development Framework underscores the importance of supportive institutions and systemic environments that enable those human capacities to thrive. This integration forms the conceptual foundation guiding the analysis of capacity gaps and training needs within Zanzibar's M&E workforce.

3.2. Empirical Review

Empirical studies have extensively explored the link between capacity, training and performance evaluation across various contexts, both globally and regionally. In Tanzania, Mgaya and Mrope (2021) identified lack of training and limited analytical skills as major barriers to effective monitoring and evaluation in Local Government Authorities (LGAs). Their study revealed that many officers rely on outdated

methods due to inadequate professional development and lack of exposure to digital M&E tools. Similarly, Ali and Suleiman (2022) found that weak implementation of performance appraisal systems in Zanzibar was largely due to limited technical capacity, insufficient institutional support, and lack of continuous training opportunities. Studies from Kenya also align with these findings. Wanyonyi and Nyambura (2023) reported that institutional capacity has a direct effect on employee productivity and evaluation effectiveness, showing that organizations with clear structures, training policies and supportive leadership produce more accurate and timely performance reports. Comparable research in Uganda by Okello and Nabirye (2022) further confirmed that insufficient M&E training reduces data utilization and weakens evidence-based decision-making in public projects.

At the continental level, AfrEA (2022) highlighted that many African countries still face critical human resource and institutional challenges in implementing strong M&E systems, emphasizing the need for targeted training programs and coordinated policy support. Likewise, World Bank (2020) and UNDP (2020) stress that capacity development initiatives should focus not only on technical skills but also on organizational culture, knowledge sharing and leadership commitment.

3.3. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship among the key variables of the study: capacity dimensions, training programs, and quality of performance evaluation. The framework is guided by the Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1993), which emphasizes the role of skills, knowledge, and education in enhancing productivity, and the Capacity Development Framework (UNDP, 2009), which highlights capacity development at individual, institutional, and systemic levels. In this study, capacity dimensions (skills, knowledge, resources, and institutional support) are treated as the independent variables. These factors represent the level of competence and support available to M&E officers in performing their duties. The training programs (frequency, coverage and relevance) act as a mediating variable, serving as a bridge that enhances the relationship between capacity dimensions and performance evaluation quality. Finally, the dependent variable is the quality of performance evaluation, which is assessed through its utilization, timeliness, and

accuracy. The framework assumes that adequate skills, knowledge, resources and institutional support positively influence the quality of performance evaluation. However, this relationship can be strengthened when relevant and frequent training programs are provided. Conversely, if capacity gaps and limited training persist, the overall performance evaluation quality may remain low, affecting evidence based decision-making in public institutions.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework (Field data, 2025)

4.0. METHODS

This study adopted a mixed methods research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to allow for comprehensive analysis of the capacity gaps and training needs in performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce. The quantitative component enabled the researcher to measure relationships among variables statistically, while the qualitative component provided deeper insights into perceptions, experiences, and contextual factors influencing M&E capacity (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The integration of both approaches enhances the validity, reliability, and richness of the findings. The study was conducted in Zanzibar, focusing on public institutions and departments under the Zanzibar Development Plan (ZADEP) framework. These institutions play key roles in monitoring and evaluation of government programs and policies, making them relevant for assessing M&E capacity and training needs. The target population comprised Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) officers and related staff working within Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) under the ZADEP implementation structure. These officers

are directly involved in performance evaluation, data management, and reporting activities within their respective organizations. The sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula, which provides a simplified method to calculate a representative sample from a given population: $n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$. Where: n = sample size, N = total population and e = margin of error (0.05 or 5%) in our case $N = 240$ Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) officers, therefore, $(n = 240 / (1 + 240(0.05)^2) = 150)$ Thus, a total of 150 respondents were selected for the study. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from various ministries and departments. Within each stratum, respondents were selected randomly to minimize bias. For qualitative data, purposive sampling was used to identify key informants, including senior officers and departmental heads with significant experience in M&E activities.

Two main instruments were employed for data collection in this study: structured questionnaires and key informant interviews. The structured questionnaire, designed using a five-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) was administered to collect quantitative data from respondents. It comprised sections on demographic characteristics, capacity dimensions, training programs, and the quality of performance evaluation. In addition, semi-structured interview guides were utilized to collect qualitative data from key informants such as senior M&E officers, directors, and policy implementers. This mixed approach enabled to obtain both numerical and in-depth contextual information, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of the institutional and systemic factors influencing performance evaluation within the Zanzibar M&E workforce.

4.1. Regression Model Specification

To examine the relationship between capacity dimensions, training programs and the quality of performance evaluation, the study employed a multiple regression model. This model was designed to test both the direct and mediating effects of the independent and mediating variables on the dependent variable. The general model was specified as follows:

$$QPE = \beta_0 + \beta_1SK + \beta_2KN + \beta_3RS + \beta_4IS + \beta_5FR + \beta_6CV + \beta_7RL + \varepsilon$$

Where: SK = Skills, KN = Knowledge, RS = Resources, IS = Institutional Support, FR=Training Frequency, CV = Training Coverage, RL = Training Relevance, β_0 = Constant term (intercept) $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ and β_7 = Regression coefficients representing the magnitude and direction of the relationships and ε = Error term.

5.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' demographic characteristics

A total of **150 respondents** participated in the study, comprising Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) officers from various public institutions under the Zanzibar Development Program (ZADEP). The results show that **54% of respondents were male**, while **46% were female**, indicating a relatively balanced gender distribution among M&E personnel. The **average age** of respondents was approximately **36.7 years**, with the majority (**37.3%**) falling within the 30–39 age group, followed by those aged 40–49 years (**25.3%**).

In terms of educational attainment, most respondents (**44.7%**) held a **bachelor's degree**, while **19.3%** possessed **diploma** and **18.0%** had **master's degrees**. A smaller proportion (**4.7%**) had attained **PhD qualifications** and **13.3%** had other forms of post-secondary education such as certificates or advanced diploma. These findings indicate that the majority of M&E officers are well-educated and equipped with the foundational academic background necessary for their professional roles.

Regarding training exposure, only **38%** of the respondents reported having received **formal M&E training** within the past two years, whereas **62%** had not attended any structured capacity-building programs. This suggests that despite the relatively strong educational profile of the respondents, opportunities for **continuous professional development** in M&E remain limited across public institutions in Zanzibar.

Table 1: Respondents' Demographic Characteristics (n = 150)

Variables	Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	81	54
	Female	69	46
Age	20–29	32	21.3
	30–39	56	37.3
	40–49	38	25.3
	50 years and above	24	16
Education Level	Diploma	29	19.3
	Bachelor's degree	67	44.7
	Master's degree	27	18
	PhD	7	4.7
	Other Certificate	20	13.3
M&E Training in the Past Two Years	Yes	57	38
	No	93	62

Source: Field data (2025)

5.1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the responses of the 150 participants regarding key aspects of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) capacity within public institutions under the Zanzibar Development Program (ZADEP). The analysis generated measures of central tendency (mean) and dispersion (standard deviation) for the major constructs examined in the study. As presented in Table 2, the mean scores for all variables were around the midpoint of the scale ($M = 3.0 - 3.6$), suggesting a generally moderate level of capacity and institutional support among M&E officers. The standard deviations, which ranged between 0.69 and 0.82, indicate moderate variation in perceptions across respondents and institutions.

Skills: The results revealed a mean score of ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.76$), signifying that respondents possess a moderate to high level of M&E skills. This finding implies that most officers are adequately skilled to undertake basic monitoring and evaluation functions, such as data collection and reporting. However, the moderate

standard deviation suggests that the distribution of skills varies across institutions, indicating a need for more uniform skill development initiatives.

Knowledge: Respondents reported a relatively high mean score for M&E knowledge ($M = 3.58$, $SD = 0.69$). This suggests that participants generally have a solid understanding of M&E concepts, principles, and methodologies. The low-to-moderate variability in responses indicates a shared perception of competence in this area, although continuous learning opportunities would further enhance their technical expertise.

Resources: The availability of resources recorded a mean score of ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 0.82$), reflecting moderate access to financial, technical, and logistical inputs necessary for conducting effective M&E activities. The higher standard deviation implies that resource availability is inconsistent across institutions while some departments have adequate support, others continue to face budgetary limitations and infrastructural gaps.

Institutional Support: Institutional support registered a mean score of ($M = 3.28$, $SD = 0.74$). This finding indicates that while there is some level of organizational backing for M&E practices, the extent and quality of such support differ among institutions. The moderate variability in responses suggests that although policies promoting M&E exist, their operationalization and enforcement are not uniform across the public sector.

Training Programs: The analysis revealed a mean score of ($M = 3.25$, $SD = 0.80$) for training programs, denoting that access to structured capacity-building opportunities in M&E is moderate. This aligns with the finding that only 38% of respondents had received formal M&E training in the past two years. The results underscore the need for enhanced and continuous professional development programs to improve M&E competencies across all institutions.

Quality of Performance Evaluation (QPE): The mean score for the quality of performance evaluation was ($M = 3.46$, $SD = 0.71$), suggesting that respondents perceive performance evaluations within their institutions to be of moderate quality. The relatively low variability indicates a general consensus that, while evaluation

practices are functional, their rigor and comprehensiveness could be improved through better training, clearer frameworks, and adequate resourcing.

Therefore, the descriptive results illustrate that M&E capacity within public institutions under ZADEP is at a moderate level, with strengths in knowledge and skills, but noticeable gaps in training, resources, and institutional support. These findings highlight the importance of investing in continuous capacity development and resource enhancement to strengthen M&E systems and improve the overall quality of performance evaluation across Zanzibar’s public sector.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Results

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
M&E officers possess the necessary skills to perform monitoring and evaluation tasks effectively	3.42	0.76	1	5
Officers demonstrate adequate knowledge of M&E concepts, methods, and procedures	3.58	0.69	1	5
Sufficient resources are available to support M&E activities within institutions	3.17	0.82	1	5
Institutional structures provide adequate support for the implementation of M&E functions	3.28	0.74	1	5
Officers have access to regular and structured M&E training programs	3.25	0.80	1	5
The quality of performance evaluation processes within institutions is satisfactory	3.46	0.71	1	5

Source: Field data, 2025

5.2. Regression Analysis

To examine the influence of the specific components of capacity dimensions and training programs on the quality of performance evaluation (QPE), a multiple regression analysis was employed. This model was designed to capture both the direct and mediating effects of the independent and training-related variables on the dependent variable. The regression model is expressed as follows:

$$QPE = \beta_0 + \beta_1SK + \beta_2KN + \beta_3RS + \beta_4IS + \beta_5FR + \beta_6CV + \beta_7RL + \varepsilon$$

Where: SK = Skills, KN = Knowledge, RS = Resources, IS = Institutional Support, FR = Training Frequency, CV = Training Coverage, RL = Training Relevance, and ε = error term.

The analysis was conducted using data obtained from 150 M&E officers across various public institutions in Zanzibar. The model aimed to determine how different aspects of capacity and training influence the perceived quality of performance evaluation within the public sector.

The regression results are presented in Table 3. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.538$) indicates that approximately **53.8%** of the variation in the quality of performance evaluation can be explained by the seven predictor variables included in the model. This suggests that capacity dimensions and training-related factors jointly account for more than half of the observed changes in evaluation quality among the Zanzibar M&E workforce. The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 24.60$, $p < 0.001$), confirming its robustness and goodness of fit.

The results show that **skills** ($p = 0.013$), **knowledge** ($p = 0.020$), **institutional support** ($p = 0.025$), **training frequency** ($p = 0.043$), and **training relevance** ($p = 0.028$) have statistically significant positive effects on the quality of performance evaluation. This implies that enhancing M&E officers' technical competence, knowledge sharing, and institutional backing alongside regular and relevant training substantially improves the quality of evaluation practices.

Conversely, **resources** ($p = 0.112$) and **training coverage** ($p = 0.089$) were not statistically significant at the 0.05 level, indicating that while these factors contribute

to the evaluation process, their impact is relatively weaker compared to other variables.

Therefore, the findings highlight that technical skills, professional knowledge, and supportive institutional environments reinforced through frequent and relevant training programs play a critical role in strengthening the quality, accuracy, and utilization of performance evaluation outcomes within Zanzibar's public sector institutions.

Table 3: Regression Results for the Effect of Capacity Dimensions and Training Programs on QPE
(N = 150)

Predictor (V)	β Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Constant (β_0)	0.654	0.229	2.86	0.005	—
Skills (SK)	0.178	0.071	2.51	0.013	Significant
Knowledge (KN)	0.161	0.068	2.36	0.020	Significant
Resources (RS)	0.093	0.058	1.60	0.112	Not Significant
Institutional Support (IS)	0.147	0.065	2.26	0.025	Significant
Training Frequency (FR)	0.112	0.055	2.04	0.043	Significant
Training Coverage (CV)	0.087	0.051	1.71	0.089	Not Significant
Training Relevance (RL)	0.134	0.060	2.23	0.028	Significant
R ²	0.538				
Adjusted R ²	0.516				
F-Statistic	24.60			0.000	Significant

5.3. Hypothesis Testing

This section presents the results of hypothesis testing based on the regression analysis discussed in the preceding section. The tests were conducted to determine

whether the proposed null hypotheses (H_{01} – H_{03}) are supported or rejected in light of the field data obtained from 150 M&E officers across various public institutions in Zanzibar.

H₀₁: *Capacity dimensions (skills, knowledge, resources, and institutional support) do not significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce.*

H_{01} was tested using multiple regression analysis by comparing the independent variables (skills, knowledge, resources, and institutional support) with the dependent variable (quality of performance evaluation). The results in Table 4.1 show that skills ($p = 0.013$), knowledge ($p = 0.020$), and institutional support ($p = 0.025$) have statistically significant positive relationships with the quality of performance evaluation, as their p -values are less than 0.05. However, resources ($p = 0.112$) were found to have no statistically significant relationship with performance evaluation quality.

These findings therefore reject the null hypothesis H_{01} and support the alternative hypothesis H_1 that capacity dimensions specifically skills, knowledge, and institutional support significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce.

H₀₂: *Training programs (frequency, coverage and relevance) do not mediate the relationship between capacity dimensions and the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce.*

H_{02} was tested using the same regression framework, focusing on the mediating role of training programs between capacity dimensions and performance evaluation quality. The findings indicate that training frequency ($p = 0.043$) and training relevance ($p = 0.028$) are statistically significant, while training coverage ($p = 0.089$) is not. This implies that regular and relevant training programs strengthen the relationship between M&E capacity and evaluation quality. Consequently, H_{02} is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_2 is supported training programs partially mediate the relationship between capacity dimensions and the quality of performance evaluation in Zanzibar's public sector institutions.

H₀₃: *Training programs do not significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce.*

The third hypothesis was also examined using regression coefficients for the training program variables (frequency, coverage, and relevance). The results (Table 4.1) reveal that two of the three components training frequency ($p = 0.043$) and training relevance ($p = 0.028$) have a significant positive effect on the quality of performance evaluation. Since the associated p-values are below the 0.05 significance level, this finding leads to the rejection of H₀₃ and supports the alternative hypothesis H₃, which asserts that training programs significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar M&E workforce

Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results			
Hypothesis	Statement	Decision	Interpretation
H ₀₁	Capacity dimensions do not significantly influence quality of performance evaluation	Rejected	Skills, knowledge, and institutional support significantly influence evaluation quality
H ₀₂	Training programs do not mediate the relationship between capacity dimensions and evaluation quality	Rejected	Training frequency and relevance strengthen this relationship
H ₀₃	Training programs do not significantly influence quality of performance evaluation	Rejected	Training programs have a direct positive influence on evaluation quality

6.0. DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between capacity dimensions, training programs, and the quality of performance evaluation among Zanzibar’s Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workforce. The regression and hypothesis testing results indicate that skills, knowledge, and institutional support

significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation, while training frequency and training relevance play a mediating and direct role in enhancing performance outcomes. These results confirm that capacity development remains a central determinant of evaluation effectiveness in public institutions.

The finding that skills and knowledge have significant positive effects on the quality of performance evaluation supports the propositions of Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1993) which argues that investment in education, skills, and training enhances productivity and performance. In the context of this study, M&E officers who possess stronger technical and analytical competencies are better equipped to design, conduct and utilize performance evaluations. This is consistent with studies by Mgaya and Mrope (2021) and Okello and Nabirye (2022) which found that officers with advanced analytical and reporting skills are more capable of producing reliable and evidence-based evaluation reports. The implication is that capacity building initiatives in Zanzibar should prioritize technical training in evaluation design, data analysis and reporting to strengthen evidence-informed policy making.

The study also revealed that institutional support significantly contributes to the quality of performance evaluation. This suggests that beyond individual competencies, organizational structures and enabling environments are critical for sustaining effective M&E systems. Institutions that provide adequate policy guidance, logistical support and incentives for performance monitoring tend to produce higher-quality evaluations. This aligns with the UNDP Capacity Development Framework (2009) which emphasizes that capacity must be developed at individual, institutional and systemic levels for long-term sustainability. Similar conclusions were reached by Ali and Suleiman (2022) in their assessment of performance appraisal implementation in Zanzibar, where inadequate institutional mechanisms were found to hinder effective evaluation practices.

On the other hand, resources and training coverage did not show statistically significant effects on evaluation quality. This may indicate that while funding and coverage are necessary, they are not sufficient in isolation to improve performance evaluation quality. What matters more is the relevance and consistency of training, as shown by the significance of training frequency and training relevance in this study.

Sporadic or generalized training sessions may not yield measurable improvement unless they are aligned with institutional needs and delivered regularly. These findings resonate with Wanyonyi and Nyambura (2023), who emphasized that the alignment between training content and job requirements determines its overall impact on performance outcomes.

The mediating role of training programs especially through frequency and relevance highlights the importance of continuous professional development in maintaining evaluation quality. Regular exposure to updated M&E methods, digital tools, and impact assessment techniques enhances officers' ability to generate credible and timely evaluation findings. This reflects the broader literature that views training as a key enabler of knowledge retention, innovation, and organizational learning (World Bank, 2020; AfrEA, 2022). In Zanzibar's context, where many officers reported limited training opportunities, this result underscores the need for structured and institutionalized professional development frameworks. Strengthening partnerships between government institutions, ZAMEA and local universities could therefore create sustainable platforms for M&E capacity enhancement.

Finally, these results demonstrate that the effectiveness of Zanzibar's performance evaluation system depends not only on the availability of human resources but also on the depth of their competencies, the regularity and relevance of training and the degree of institutional backing provided. The study's outcomes thus extend empirical support to both the Human Capital Theory and the Capacity Development Framework, confirming that capacity building interventions that combine individual skill development with institutional strengthening are more likely to yield sustainable improvements in evaluation quality. The discussion highlights that bridging existing capacity gaps requires a dual approach strengthening individual competencies through frequent and context relevant training and simultaneously enhancing institutional environments through supportive policies, resource allocation and coordination mechanisms. Addressing these factors holistically will ensure that the Zanzibar public sector develops a professional and resilient M&E workforce capable of generating reliable performance evidence for policy and decision making.

7.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Conclusion

This study set out to examine the relationship between capacity dimensions, training programs, and the quality of performance evaluation among the Zanzibar Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) workforce. The results from the regression analysis and hypothesis testing demonstrate that technical skills, knowledge, and institutional support significantly influence the quality of performance evaluation. Furthermore, the findings reveal that training frequency and relevance play a key role in mediating and directly improving evaluation quality, confirming the importance of continuous professional development in strengthening M&E capacity.

The study concludes that the quality of performance evaluation in Zanzibar's public sector is largely determined by the level of technical competence, the consistency and relevance of training programs and the extent of institutional support provided to M&E officers. The results affirm both the Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1993) and the Capacity Development Framework (UNDP, 2009), which jointly emphasize that performance and productivity improve when individuals and institutions invest in systematic capacity development.

Despite moderate levels of skills and knowledge among M&E officers, the study highlights a misalignment between institutional responsibilities and available workforce capacity, coupled with weak collaboration between government institutions, academic bodies, and professional associations such as ZAMEA. This gap reflects systemic limitations in policy coordination, resource allocation, and institutional support mechanisms. Consequently, while progress has been made in integrating M&E functions within public institutions, the sustainability and effectiveness of performance evaluation practices remain constrained by inconsistent training coverage, limited institutional engagement, and underutilization of local expertise.

Therefore, addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach that not only enhances individual competencies but also strengthens institutional and systemic environments that support effective evaluation practices.

7.2 Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following policy recommendations are proposed to strengthen performance evaluation systems and close existing capacity gaps within Zanzibar's M&E workforce:

To begin with, it is essential for the government through the Ministry of Finance and Planning in collaboration with the Zanzibar Monitoring and Evaluation Association (ZAMEA) to institutionalize a continuous professional training framework. Such a framework should provide regular, relevant, and competency-based learning opportunities for M&E officers across all public institutions. Continuous training will ensure that practitioners remain updated on emerging methodologies, analytical tools, and evaluation standards required for effective performance measurement.

Furthermore, collaboration between government institutions, ZAMEA, local universities, and regional training centers should be strengthened to design and implement accredited M&E courses that reflect Zanzibar's contextual realities. Closer partnerships between these stakeholders would promote contextualized learning, build a pipeline of skilled evaluators, and reduce the current dependence on external consultants for evaluation assignments.

In addition, the government should conduct regular capacity audits within ministries, departments, and agencies to identify gaps in skills, resources, and institutional arrangements. Findings from such audits would provide evidence for targeted interventions and informed resource planning to improve the quality of performance evaluations.

Equally important is the need to increase institutional support and resource allocation for M&E activities. Policy frameworks should prioritize adequate budgetary and logistical resources to enable officers to conduct timely data collection, analysis, and reporting. Strengthened institutional backing will enhance the quality, utilization, and credibility of evaluation results used in policy formulation and decision-making.

The development of a professional certification system for M&E practitioners is also recommended. Working jointly with ZAMEA and academic institutions, the

government should introduce an accreditation mechanism that standardizes professional competencies, promotes accountability, and fosters a culture of excellence in evaluation practice across the public sector.

Lastly, there is a need to promote knowledge sharing and peer learning through cross-institutional platforms such as workshops, professional forums, and annual evaluation conferences. These initiatives will foster collaboration, encourage innovation, and strengthen a culture of evidence-based decision-making across public institutions.

REFERENCES

1. AfrEA. (2022). *African Evaluation Association annual report 2022: Strengthening evaluation capacity in Africa*. African Evaluation Association.
2. Ali, H., & Suleiman, Z. (2022). Assessing implementation of performance appraisal in Zanzibar public sector. *African Journal of Management and Administration*, 10(2), 89–103.
3. Becker, G. S. (1993). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education* (3rd ed.). University of Chicago Press.
4. Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
5. Mgya, E., & Mrope, N. (2021). The role of performance management in local government authorities in Tanzania. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 34(5), 763–777.
6. Mtega, W. P., & Malekani, A. J. (2021). Building evaluation capacity in developing countries: Lessons from Tanzania. *African Evaluation Journal*, 9(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.xxxxx/aej.v9i1>
7. Okello, D., & Nabirye, R. (2022). Capacity development and utilization of monitoring and evaluation data in Uganda's public sector. *African Journal of Development Studies*, 12(3), 201–217.

8. REPOA. (2021). *Strengthening monitoring and evaluation capacity in Tanzania's public administration* (Policy Brief No. 32). REPOA.
9. Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar. (2021). *Zanzibar monitoring, evaluation and learning framework (Z-MELF)*. Ministry of State, President's Office – Finance and Planning.
10. Schultz, T. W. (2018). *Investment in human capital*. University of Chicago Press.
11. United Nations Development Programme. (2009). *Capacity development: A UNDP primer*.
12. United Republic of Tanzania. (2020). *National framework for monitoring and evaluation*. Ministry of Finance and Planning.
13. Wanyonyi, A., & Nyambura, M. (2023). Influence of flexible work practices on employee performance in the Public Service Commission, Kenya. *International Journal of Management and Business Research*, 13(1), 45–60.
14. World Bank. (2020). *Improving monitoring and evaluation capacity in Africa: Lessons from the CLEAR initiative*. World Bank Group.